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ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

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- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
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05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
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05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
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05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
05.08.06 – "G'ildirakli va gusenisali mashinalar va ularni ishlatish" (texnika fanlari)
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05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
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08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
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08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK

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SME INTERNATIONALIZATION IN EMERGING ECONOMIES: DIGITALIZATION, ADAPTIVE CAPABILITIES, AND IMPLICATIONS FOR FEMALE ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract: This study uses qualitative thematic analysis of semi-structured interviews with export-oriented businesses to investigate SME internationalization. The results demonstrate that flexible tactics, market adaptability, and adaptive management are critical to global success. Competitiveness in international markets is also influenced by supply chain resilience and sustainable practices. The report offers useful recommendations for encouraging female entrepreneurship in global company and emphasizes the significance of technology, adaptability, and sustainability.

Keywords: SME internationalization, Digital transformation, Dynamic capabilities, Sustainability, Emerging economies, Female entrepreneurship.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot eksportga yo'naltirilgan korxonalar bilan o'tkazilgan yarim tuzilgan intervyular asosida sifatli tematik tahlil usulidan foydalanib, kichik va o'rta biznesning (KOB) xalqaro bozorga chiqishini o'rganadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, moslashuvchan strategiyalar, bozorga tez moslashish va adaptiv boshqaruv global muvaffaqiyat uchun muhim omillardir. Xalqaro bozorlarda raqobatbardoshlikka ta'minot zanjiri barqarorligi hamda barqaror rivojlanish amaliyotlari ham sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot global biznesda ayollar tadbirkorligini rivojlantirish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar beradi hamda texnologiya, moslashuvchanlik va barqarorlikning ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: KOB xalqaro integratsiyasi, raqamli transformatsiya, dinamik imkoniyatlar, barqarorlik, rivojlanayotgan iqtisodiyotlar, ayollar tadbirkorligi.

Аннотация: В данном исследовании используется качественный тематический анализ полуструктурированных интервью с экспортно-ориентированными предприятиями для изучения интернационализации малого и среднего бизнеса (МСБ). Результаты показывают, что гибкие стратегии, адаптация к рынку и адаптивное управление являются ключевыми факторами глобального успеха. Конкурентоспособность на международных рынках также зависит от устойчивости цепочек поставок и практик устойчивого развития. В работе представлены практические рекомендации по развитию женского предпринимательства в глобальном бизнесе, а также подчеркивается важность технологий, адаптивности и устойчивости.

Ключевые слова: интернационализация МСБ, цифровая трансформация, динамические способности, устойчивость, развивающиеся экономики, женское предпринимательство.

INTRODUCTION

Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are undergoing significant change as a result of digitalization, which is changing how businesses function, interact, and compete in international marketplaces. SMEs are becoming more able to lower transaction costs, enhance coordination, and more effectively access global markets through the use of information and communication technologies (ICT), digital platforms, including data-driven systems. Digital technologies are therefore widely acknowledged as significant facilitators of SME internationalization and competitiveness in the global market [1].

Nevertheless, not all SMEs are able to convert digital investments into long-term global performance, even with the increasing use of digital tools. According to recent studies, the effects of digitalization depend not only on the use of technology itself but also on how businesses manage and incorporate it into their organizational and strategic processes. Specifically, whether digital transformation results in significant global outcomes depends on technology management, which is defined as the alignment, execution, and exploitation of digital resources within a firm's strategy [2].

However, new evidence suggests that not all entrepreneurs benefit equally from digitalization. In the context of digital transformation and internationalization in developing countries, female entrepreneurs in particular constitute a significant but understudied group. The use and management of technology for global expansion by female-led SMEs may be constrained by structural limitations such as restricted access to resources, networks, and digital skills. However, there is still a lack of empirical evidence on these differences, particularly in contexts like Uzbekistan, where SME development and digital transformation are evolving rapidly [3]. Thus, with an emphasis on female entrepreneurship within the context of Uzbekistan, this study explores the role of technology management in SME internationalization. By doing so, it aims to provide a more nuanced understanding of how digitalization influences global performance and whether these effects differ across entrepreneurial groups.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Studies on female entrepreneurship show that, especially in emerging economies, women-owned enterprises are becoming increasingly crucial to economic growth, innovation, and job creation. However, compared to male entrepreneurs, female entrepreneurs frequently encounter structural obstacles that may hinder business growth and international expansion, such as restricted access to financial resources, weaker professional networks, and institutional limitations. In the context of digital transformation, where the utilization of technology and digital skills is a crucial factor in determining competitiveness, these limitations become particularly significant [4].

According to recent research, digital technologies can offer female entrepreneurs' substantial opportunities by lowering traditional barriers to entry, facilitating flexible business models, and increasing access to international markets through digital platforms and e-commerce systems [5]. Therefore, by increasing visibility, customer reach, and operational efficiency without requiring substantial physical infrastructure, digitalization may serve as an empowering factor for women-led SMEs. However, in addition to having access to technology, female entrepreneurs must also possess digital skills, strategic management competencies, and institutional support networks in order to fully benefit from digital transformation.

The importance of digitalization and advanced technology in influencing SME internationalization is becoming more widely acknowledged in recent research. Evidence from systematic reviews demonstrates that digitalization facilitates learning, value chain restructuring, and firm scalability, all of which contribute to global expansion [6]. Through information and communication technology (ICT) systems and digital platforms, digital technologies lower coordination costs and make it easier to access global markets. However, most studies primarily conceptualize digitalization as an enabling factor rather than examining how businesses strategically manage their technological resources.

Empirical studies also show that digital transformation affects companies' export behavior both directly and indirectly through productivity-related mechanisms [7]. Although these results demonstrate measurable trade benefits, they mainly address digital adoption rather than technology management practices. Investigations on online platforms and SME internationalization further indicate that internal digital skills moderate the success of platform participation, suggesting that organizational and managerial factors are critical for international outcomes [8].

Theoretical perspectives in the reviewed literature are influenced by network approaches, resource-based views, and stage models of internationalization. Studies of SMEs in emerging economies highlight institutional effects and learning processes as key factors shaping international expansion [9]. Previous research on the development of SME information systems shows that organizational focus and managerial priorities, rather than mere technology availability, determine capability development [10]. These findings imply that technology-related outcomes are embedded within broader institutional and strategic contexts.

The strategic alignment of technological activities with international growth objectives emerges as another important factor in the literature. Research shows that digital transformation generates long-term global benefits when it is integrated into strategic frameworks and supported by managerial commitment [11]. SMEs can restructure organizational systems, enhance cross-border collaboration, and improve international responsiveness more effectively when digital tools are embedded into core strategic planning processes. This perspective supports the view that technology management should be understood as a comprehensive managerial capability rather than as isolated technological adoption.

Business model transformation is another critical strategy SMEs use to overcome challenges associated with international expansion. Reim et al. [12] argue that internationalization often requires firms to redesign their value propositions, revenue models, and operational structures rather than simply transferring domestic models to foreign markets. Technological capabilities facilitate this process by enabling cross-border coordination,

service innovation, and digital integration. However, successful internationalization depends on the deliberate integration of technology into business model innovation processes. This highlights the role of technology management as a flexible mechanism through which SMEs can adapt their organizational configurations and value creation processes to global market demands.

Recent empirical studies have also examined the relationship between innovation types and SME internationalization. According to Ramdani [13], not all forms of innovation exert equal influence on export performance. Based on innovation theory and the Resource-Based View, the findings indicate that product innovation has a stronger positive impact on export propensity than process or service innovation. This suggests that the development of new or improved products is more closely associated with international competitiveness than improvements in internal efficiency alone. The study reinforces the importance of aligning technological and innovative capabilities with market-oriented strategies.

The growing significance of cross-border digital platforms has also transformed how exporters in emerging economies build international capabilities. Research indicates that firms employ adaptive strategies when using digital platforms and that capability development is essential for effective internationalization [14]. From a capability-based perspective, digital platforms are not merely transactional channels but environments requiring continuous strategic adaptation, learning, and organizational development. Exporters in developing countries can benefit from digital platforms only if they actively develop adaptive capabilities to respond to institutional differences and market volatility. This perspective further supports the view that technology management involves continuous strategic adjustment and capability building rather than simple participation in digital markets.

However, most research on SME digitalization treats firms as gender-neutral entities, overlooking the possibility that entrepreneurial gender may influence how technology is adopted and managed. This gap is particularly important in emerging economies, where disparities in access to resources and technology may lead to unequal digitalization and internationalization outcomes for female-led enterprises.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to supplement the analysis of SME digitization and internationalization in Uzbekistan, this study uses a qualitative approach. Four owners of small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) and one representative of a large organization participated in semi-structured interviews. The goal of the qualitative component is to investigate how businesses actually adopt, manage, and integrate digital technologies, and how these processes affect their global operations. The SMEs in this study were selected based on their participation in commercial activities where digital technologies are used for cooperation, communication, and market expansion. To provide a comparative perspective on differences in digital infrastructure, organizational structure, and the strategic use of technology, an interview with a large enterprise was included. Key topics covered in the interview protocol include platform utilization, innovation activities, digital transformation processes, technology management practices, and interaction with foreign markets. The fact that all interviews were conducted with male managers or entrepreneurs reflects the accessibility of respondents during the data collection process.

The results reveal important aspects of entrepreneurial competence that are frequently discussed in the literature on female entrepreneurship, particularly in relation to decision-making under uncertainty, resource constraints, and adaptive market behavior, even though the interviews were conducted with SME managers in export-oriented firms. The study acknowledges female entrepreneurship as a significant contextual dimension in SME digitization, despite the fact that gender was not included as an empirical variable in the qualitative dataset. This aspect is addressed in the literature review and research gap sections for further investigation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The framework was developed through a thematic analysis of qualitative interview data collected from export-oriented Uzbek SMEs, allowing for the identification of key patterns related to their internationalization processes. The findings indicate that entrepreneurial competence serves as a critical input factor, encompassing decision-making abilities such as data utilization, strategic thinking, and risk assessment, alongside constraints related to limited financial resources, digital tools, and technological capacity. In addition, market intelligence and flexibility, reflected in continuous trend monitoring, responsiveness to consumer feedback, and competitive analysis, play a significant role. These dimensions emerged from respondents' descriptions of how decisions are made in global markets under conditions of uncertainty and resource scarcity.

The analysis further reveals that firms rely on entrepreneurial mechanisms to transform both external

information and internal resources into strategic actions. Decision-making processes are highly adaptive, often driven by real-time market signals rather than formalized analytical systems, which highlights the importance of agility and responsiveness in dynamic international environments. As a result of these processes, firms achieve a range of outcomes associated with international performance, including export growth, market expansion, enhanced operational resilience, and improved competitiveness and efficiency. These outcomes reflect the ability of firms to effectively navigate uncertainty and adjust to evolving conditions in international markets, as summarized in Table 1 (Table 1).

Table 1.
Conceptual Table

INPUT FACTORS	→	PROCESS	→	OUTCOMES
Decision-Making Skills (risk assessment, strategy, data use)	→	Entrepreneurial Cognition & Strategy	→	SME International Performance (export growth, resilience, innovation)
Resource Constraints (limited technology, finance, tools)	→	Adaptive Resource Management	→	Operational Efficiency & Flexibility
Market Intelligence & Adaptability (competition, clients, trends)	→	Opportunity Recognition & Adjustment	→	Market Expansion & Competitiveness

The paradigm emphasizes how adaptive decision-making under resource constraints significantly influences entrepreneurial success in SME internationalization when viewed through the lens of female entrepreneurship. This aligns with research indicating that female entrepreneurs frequently operate in resource-constrained environments, requiring adaptive, relational, and opportunity-driven decision-making strategies. As a result, the model advances the understanding of how entrepreneurial competence functions in SMEs within emerging economies, particularly under conditions of uncertainty and limited resources.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Through thematic analysis of interviews with export-oriented businesses, this study investigated SME internationalization. The results demonstrate that market responsiveness, adaptive management techniques, and the capacity to modify plans in response to external changes are key factors influencing the performance of multinational businesses. Although the degree of technological adoption varies among firms, digital tools and data-driven decision-making increasingly support operational efficiency. Furthermore, maintaining competitiveness in international markets is increasingly dependent on supply chain flexibility and sustainable practices. In general, SME internationalization is shaped by strategic flexibility, technological preparedness, and environmental awareness.

Suggestions (with an emphasis on female entrepreneurship): Improve women entrepreneurs' digital skills to increase competitiveness in global markets; training in CRM, ERP, and fundamental data analytics should be expanded. Expand access to export market intelligence; better availability of reliable market research, demand analysis tools, and international trade data is essential for women-led SMEs.

Encourage environmentally friendly business practices; access to high-value export markets can be enhanced by promoting sustainable production and certification (such as ISO standards).

Enhance opportunities for international networking; export marketing initiatives, B2B platforms, and trade exhibitions should support female entrepreneurs.

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